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AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies (formerly *Apostolic Union for Clergy*) is a peer-reviewed pastoral journal for Christian leaders. It is a bimonthly published from the Papal Seminary, Pune 411014. Inspiring and brief pastoral and academic articles beneficial for Christian leaders are welcome.

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For **all editorial members**, please see www.punejournal.co.in

Printed at: Kunal Offset, 412, Kakasaheb Gadgil Rd, Shaniwar Peth, Pune 411030: Mob 98230 48871

Typeset at: Papal Seminary Centenary Computer Centre

Donations are accepted. Cheques and DD to be drawn in favour of

Apostolic Union

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Email: auc@papalseminary.in or Site: punejournal.co.in

ISSN: P-2249-1503 | E-2582-791X

Editorial

Spirituality, Wisdom and Courage

Coronavirus and COVID-19 have brought a flood of fear and uncertainty for many of us. We are forced to listen to 24-hour news cycle that terrifies us. We've been told not to leave our houses unless we must. Most of our lives are in sudden upheaval as we adjust to a "new normal" for an unforeseen amount of time. The uncertainty is unsettling.

Sometimes we don't know where to turn for support. We feel lost. While this global pandemic is unique in many ways, these feelings of fear and isolation are nothing new. We may remember that our religious and spiritual traditions have been poised to respond to times of crisis since time immemorial (St. Jude Children's Research Hospital, 2021).

Some common themes that emerged during this pandemic, especially the second wave are:

Grief: While we normally think of grief only in connection with the death of a loved one, we can have the same feelings of loss when we are facing uncertainty.

Cite as: Pandikattu, Kuruvilla (2021). Editorial: Spirituality, Wisdom and Courage (Version 1.0). AUC: Asian Journal of Religious Studies, May-June 2021(66/3), 3–5.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo. 4716065>

We could all be grieving losses in this time. These may include loss of:

- Some of our own friends and relatives
- A “normal” daily routine
- Time with friends and family
- A feeling of we are in control of
- Spiritual community, sacraments, and prayers

Sometimes when we experience grief, we feel shocked, anxious, fearful, sad, powerless, angry, or helpless. What we need to remember is that all these feelings and many others are normal. Being able to acknowledge where we are emotionally and spiritually can be empowering.

Let us be kind to ourselves as we navigate through our emotions. We can remember that we are all together despite the distance we are forced to maintain.

Lord, knowing fully well that you are the Lord of this tragedy we experience, we surrender ourselves to you. We pray for all those who have died of this terrible sickness. As we grieve their parting, may we draw strength from your tragic death and glorious resurrection.

Prayer and Wisdom: Often in times of distress and pain, we turn our minds to God. This can be difficult if the places we normally go to worship are closed right now. It can be helpful to try to recreate this environment at home (St. Jude Children’s Research Hospital, 2021). Many houses of worship are posting services online. Let us participate in them and try to draw hope and strength for ourselves and those who are close to us. Let us use this chance to recollect ourselves and make our live deeper and wiser.

Courage and Hope: Recognising that things are bad, we cannot afford to close our eyes to the suffering and agony of all around us. While keeping our eyes wide open to their angst, can we also be sources of courage and hope? Though difficult, we can still spread awareness, attention and attentiveness, with courage and hope. We do know that things are very difficult. But we can still count on Him, who has gone through terrible betrayal and pain. We need to be cautious and courageous. Not fearful and frightened. Let us be catalysts of hope in these troubled times.

A simple prayer we can repeat is: Lord, knowing fully well that you are the Lord of this tragedy we experience, we surrender ourselves to you. We pray for all those who have died of this terrible sickness. As we grieve their parting, may we draw strength from your tragic death and glorious resurrection.

It is a terrible experience to imagine that we may not be there to touch the next issue of our journal. Still, life goes on! It must!

In this sense, we can draw wisdom from the wounds that we have been dealt with. We do know for sure that this too will pass away. We shall overcome. Together. Fear not, let us be courageous (Pandikattu, 2020), with the Lord who has suffered and risen!

Reference

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. (2020). *Have Courage, I am with You: Christian Responses to Covid-19*. New Delhi, Media House.

St. Jude Children’s Research Hospital. (2021). *Faith and Spirituality During Coronavirus*. Memphis. <https://together.stjude.org/en-us/families/spirituality-and-faith/faith-spirituality-coronavirus.html>

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